
3D HUMAN POSE ESTIMATION USING MULTI CAMERA

UNDERGRADUATE PROJECT
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ABSTRACT

This work focuses on estimating 3D Human Poses from video recorded using multiple camera system. Each of the camera placed at some different position and angle. For demo we used the camera stream from two camera placed at 90° to each other, this video is available via the HumanEva I dataset [1]. Numbers of previous work have been done in this domain in past. Some of them directly try to estimate 3D poses out of the given video stream while some of them first finds 2D keypoints followed by 3D pose estimate using those 2D keypoints. Our work followed on lines similar to the later one, we first find the 2D keypoints (refer section 2.2) for the output video of the two camera. And then we estimate 3D poses by solving a set of equations formed using the camera's parameters i.e. its rotation and translation matrix (refer section 2.3). To find 2D keypoints we used pre-trained weights of Cascaded Pyramidal Networks (CPN) [2] which generates the heatmaps for 17 different key points on human body. Our method estimated the 3D poses well for the tested cases but we were not able to test and verify numerical results on complete HumanEva - I dataset because of resource limitation. Further, in place of using camera parameters to estimate 3D poses we are trying to learn simple multi layer neural network model to learn a transformation from 2D keypoints of multiple camera to 3D poses. The code for implementation is available on github¹.

1 Introduction

3D human pose estimation is the task of finding the 3D pose of the humans present in an image or sequence of images that matches the spatial position of that human. Mostly

¹<https://github.com/shashikg/3DHPMC>

we try to find the 3D position for a set of specified keypoints on human body like eye, nose, shoulders, elbow, hand, hip, knee, ankle, etc. This comes out to be an important task in computer vision and contribute into various scientific and consumer domains such as surveillance system, human-robot interaction, virtual/ augmented reality, action understanding, etc.

In past, various research have been done in estimating 3D human poses. Some important works in this domain includes, Burenus et al. 2013 [3] Pictorial Structure Method (PSM) for 3D poses in which the human body parts are considered as an articulated structure and the method models each of the body part and spatial relationship between them using multiple camera view. Li and Chan 2014 [4] estimated 3D poses using deep convolutional neural network. They trained the model using two type of tasks: 1) A keypoint regression and 2) A keypoint detection. Keypoint regression strategy estimates the position of keypoints in the given image and keypoint detection strategy classify a local position on the image to a specific keypoint. Chen and Ramanan 2017 [5] estimated 3D human poses using 2D human poses. They first estimate the 2D poses and then match those 2D poses to some 3D exemplars, the best matching exemplar is chosen as the 3D estimate for the found 2D pose. Martinez et al. 2017 [6] introduced a simple yet effective baseline model for estimating 3D pose from 2D pose. They built a simple neural network architecture which predicts the 3D poses from a given sets of 2D keypoints from a single camera image. Pavllo et al. 2019 further refined this method by using temporal information i.e. estimating 3D poses using 2D pose of sequence of three images at different time.

Our method uses multiple camera view as in the work of Burenus et al. but instead on learning relationship between various body parts, we estimate 2D joints using SOTA method for both camera separately and impose the information from both to estimate our 3D pose (Sec 2.3). We show that a simple method of estimating unknowns using a MLE estimate can easily estimate right positions for 3D poses from 2D keypoints. Our method is different from other methods as in Chen and Ramanan 2017 [5] and Martinez et al. 2017 [6] because we are not relying on information from single camera. If we look at most of the application of 3D pose estimate, most of them can easily accommodate to have a two camera system instead of one. Which will probably improve the computation cost for 3D pose estimate from 2D poses. Also, we provide a general code repository which can be easily modified to use in a completely different setting by simply changing the camera parameters i.e. rotation matrix and translation vectors.

2 Implementation

2.1 Person Detection

For person detection we used SSD MobileNet v1 [7] model trained on COCO 2017 detection dataset. Images from both camera were fed to the model using TensorFlow API². This classifies the image regions into different classes. We select the the region corresponding to

²https://github.com/tensorflow/models/tree/master/research/object_detection

"person" class and then crop a region around it such that cropped image have a ratio of 4 : 3. We select this ratio because the CPN model used for generating heatmaps for 2D keypoints was trained on a image of size 384 x 288 (a ratio of 4 : 3). So, this ensures that we do not distort the image resolution when we feed the cropped images into CPN model. Refer Fig. 1

Figure 1: Person Detection

2.2 2D Keypoint Detection

For detecting 2D keypoints, based on performances in terms of accuracy and efficiency of past research we tried out two different deep net methods. We first tried with Zhe Cao et al. 2017 [8] PAFs based model (with MobileNet³ as the base model) for efficiency purpose but we find that this produces a lot of flickering in the estimated 2D poses. So for our final model we selected CPN [2] (with ResNet-50 [9] as the base model) for our 2D keypoint detection module. We used pre-trained model which were trained on COCO dataset⁴. We were not able to fine tune these model on HumanEva-I dataset because of our resource limitation. The CPN model takes input images of size 384 x 288 and produces 17 heatmaps corresponding to following keypoints: eyes, ears, nose, shoulders, elbow, hand, hip, knee, and foot. The generated heatmap is of size 96 x 72. To find the corresponding keypoints we resize the generated heatmaps to 384 x 288. Then apply a gaussian filter of size 21 x 21 with $\sigma = 5$ so as to smooth the output heatmaps. (Refer Fig. 2 for a sample of heatmaps generated for 15 keypoints).

Finally, for each of the heatmaps we find the index for the maximum activation and take that as the position for corresponding keypoint. After calculating the keypoint for the cropped image, we transform the position to the original image. We also calculated one extra keypoint for 'neck' using the detected keypoint for 'nose', 'left shoulder', and 'right shoulder'. Refer to Fig. 3 for an example of detected 2D keypoints.

³https://github.com/michalfaber/tensorflow_Realtime_Multi-Person_Pose_Estimation

⁴https://github.com/Longqi-S/keras_cpn/releases

Figure 2: Heatmaps for nose, ears, shoulders, elbow, hand, hip, knee, and foot

2.3 Estimating 3D Poses Using 2D Keypoints

Assuming a pinhole camera model, image coordinates p_c of a point P in global reference frame can be written in terms of a rotation matrix R and a translation vector T . (Eq. 1) Where R is a 3×3 matrix, T a 3×1 vector, and p_c and P are 3×1 position vectors. Therefore $p_c = [x_c, y_c, z_c]^T$ and $P = [x, y, z]^T$. Here, x_c and y_c simply denotes the points on the $N \times M$ image and z_c denotes the distance at which the image plane is from the camera.

$$p_c = R \cdot P + T \quad (1)$$

For the HumanEva-I dataset, we have the following values for rotation matrix and translation vector. (Eq. 2 3 4 5)

$$R_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.1434 & 0.9896 & 0.0092 \\ 0.1672 & 0.0334 & -0.9854 \\ -0.9754 & -0.1397 & -0.1702 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$T_1 = [-88.1 \quad 804.8 \quad 4315.3]^T \quad (3)$$

Figure 3: Detected 2D keypoints for the images from both camera

$$R_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.9654 & 0.2600 & -0.0214 \\ 0.0151 & -0.1372 & -0.9904 \\ -0.2605 & 0.9558 & -0.1364 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$T_2 = [206.1 \quad 955.7 \quad 4062.3]^T \quad (5)$$

Using these matrices and translation vector, we can form the following two equation 6 and 7. In these equations we will have total 5 unknowns z_{c1} , z_{c2} , and 3 unknowns in vector P . To solve this we further simplified this equation so as to use it for any different configuration as we want.

$$p_{c1} = R_1 \cdot P + T_1 \quad (6)$$

$$p_{c2} = R_2 \cdot P + T_2 \quad (7)$$

At the end what we want is to know the value of P . Since point P is relative to world reference frame and would simply gives us our 3D estimate for corresponding 2D keypoints. To solve the equations 6 and 7, we first eliminate P from it and then solve the resultant equation (8) to find the value of z_{c1} and z_{c2}

$$R_1^{-1} \cdot (p_{c1} - T_1) = R_2^{-1} \cdot (p_{c2} - T_2) = P \quad (8)$$

Figure 4: Estimated 3D Pose for the Available 2D Keypoints

Substituting $(p_{c1} - T_1) = p'_{c1}$ and $(p_{c2} - T_2) = p'_{c2}$ in equation 8, we get:

$$R_1^{-1} \cdot p'_{c1} = R_2^{-1} \cdot p'_{c2} = P \quad (9)$$

To simplify this equation we write $R_1^{-1} = [r_1^1 \ r_2^1 \ r_3^1]$ and similarly, $R_2^{-1} = [r_1^2 \ r_2^2 \ r_3^2]$. Where r_i^j represents a 3 x 1 i^{th} column vector of matrix R_j^{-1} . Representing $p'_{c1} = [x'_{c1} \ y'_{c1} \ z'_{c1}]^T$ and $p'_{c2} = [x'_{c2} \ y'_{c2} \ z'_{c2}]^T$. Adding these representation to equation 9 will yield equation 10:

$$[r_1^1 \ r_2^1 \ r_3^1] \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x'_{c1} \\ y'_{c1} \\ z'_{c1} \end{bmatrix} = [r_1^2 \ r_2^2 \ r_3^2] \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x'_{c2} \\ y'_{c2} \\ z'_{c2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

After some simple rearrangement in equation 10, we can arrive at following:

$$[r_3^1 \ r_3^2] \cdot \begin{bmatrix} z'_{c1} \\ -z'_{c2} \end{bmatrix} = [r_1^1 \ r_2^1 \ r_1^2 \ r_2^2] \cdot \begin{bmatrix} -x'_{c1} \\ -y'_{c1} \\ x'_{c2} \\ y'_{c2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Now, substituting $\begin{bmatrix} r_3^1 & r_3^2 \end{bmatrix} = X$ (a 3x2 matrix) and RHS of equation 11 with Y (a 3x1 column matrix). Our problem simplifies to a simple linear regression problem (equation 12) in which our unknowns i.e. weight vector is $\begin{bmatrix} z'_{c1} & -z'_{c2} \end{bmatrix}^T$.

$$X \cdot \begin{bmatrix} z'_{c1} \\ -z'_{c2} \end{bmatrix} = Y \quad (12)$$

The equation 12 can be simply solved by MLE estimate, which will give us the value for z'_{c1} and z'_{c2} (equation 13). Using this value in equation 9, we can finally compute the value for P which will be our 3D estimate for the given pairs of 2D keypoints for both the camera (Refer 4 for a sample estimate).

$$\begin{bmatrix} z'_{c1} \\ -z'_{c2} \end{bmatrix} = (X^T X)^{-1} X^T Y \quad (13)$$

References

- [1] L. Sigal, A.O. Balan, and M.J. Black. Humaneva: Synchronized video and motion capture dataset and baseline algorithm for evaluation of articulated human motion. *Int J Comput Vis*, 87(4), 2010.
- [2] Yilun Chen, Zhicheng Wang, Yuxiang Peng, Zhiqiang Zhang, Gang Yu, and Jian Sun. Cascaded pyramid network for multi-person pose estimation. *CoRR*, abs/1711.07319, 2017.
- [3] M. Burenius, J. Sullivan, and S. Carlsson. 3d pictorial structures for multiple view articulated pose estimation. In *2013 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 3618–3625, 2013.
- [4] Sijin Li and Antoni B. Chan. 3d human pose estimation from monocular images with deep convolutional neural network. *CoRR*, abs/1611.08050, 2014.
- [5] Ching-Hang Chen and Deva Ramanan. 3d human pose estimation = 2d pose estimation + matching. *CoRR*, abs/1612.06524, 2016.
- [6] Julieta Martinez, Rayat Hossain, Javier Romero, and James J. Little. A simple yet effective baseline for 3d human pose estimation. *CoRR*, abs/1705.03098, 2017.
- [7] Andrew G. Howard, Menglong Zhu, Bo Chen, Dmitry Kalenichenko, Weijun Wang, Tobias Weyand, Marco Andreetto, and Hartwig Adam. Mobilenets: Efficient convolutional neural networks for mobile vision applications. *CoRR*, abs/1704.04861, 2017.
- [8] Zhe Cao, Tomas Simon, Shih-En Wei, and Yaser Sheikh. Realtime multi-person 2d pose estimation using part affinity fields. *CoRR*, abs/1611.08050, 2016.
- [9] Kaiming He, Xiangyu Zhang, Shaoqing Ren, and Jian Sun. Deep residual learning for image recognition. *CoRR*, abs/1512.03385, 2015.